

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

CORRELATION BETWEEN ECONOMIC HUMAN RIGHTS AS THE FOUNDATION OF THE STATE ECONOMIC SYSTEM AND STATE'S CONSTITUTIONAL REGIME

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Abstract

Human rights and economic freedoms, being the basis of the state economic system and, respectively, an essential element of the social system, represent the institution in a mutual dependence with the constitutional regime. Throughout the development of the state economic system it was noted that political and state stability are possible only under the conditions of existence of a constant social composure, which, otherwise, can be obtained only if the majority of the members of society consider their economic conditions satisfactory, and vice versa, social composure is difficult to obtain and to show if the economic state of large groups of population does not allow them to satisfy their economic needs and, respectively, the economy of the state cannot offer them prospect for a decent future.

Keywords: Human rights, state economic system, constitutional regime's concept.

JEL Classification: K10, K19, K30

Introduction

The analysis of the constitutional regime's concept shows that it represent from a set of general-binding and formally-determined rules meant to regulate the organization and leadership of a state that is the holder of sovereignty and the essential factor that personifies the nation from a juridical point of view, only by the fact of its existence, has a strictly determined organization, enshrined in the supreme law – the Constitution.

In a formal aspect, the constitutional regime represents the externalization or objectification of the set of rules that regulate the organization and leadership of a state in a politico-juridical document. So, the constitutional regime, in the formal sense, in most modern states, is governed on the basis of written constitution, because only in a rule of law, the governors exercise power only by virtue of prerogatives established in an act, by which they are vested with certain functions, thus they hold prerogatives on the basis of the Constitution or a normative act with constitutional value and not of an ordinary of organic law.

Results and discussions

An inefficient economic system, which generated deficits and financial loses, causes its members to satisfy their economic interests through methods, sometimes contrary to the law, which results in the rooting of the negative phenomenon called corruption, both at the local level and at the central level of the public administration, which leads to a social imbalance in the state.

Historically, economic dissatisfaction pushes society to change the structure of property in the state in general, or the right to property in particular, which otherwise represent a fundamental economic rights of Man, changing both "static property relations, which are related to the person's possession of goods and express their belonging, and dynamic property relations,

which are related to the passage of goods from one owner to another, the process of moving good in the state takes place"¹.

The redistribution activity mentioned above is constantly facing certain limits, manifested mainly through the phenomena of political revolutions. In fact, all political revolutions can be analyzed as redistributions of property rights beyond the constitutional limits of previous social organizations. The French Revolution, for example, repealed the property rights of nobles in favor of the bourgeoisie, in violation of the Constitution, as the supreme law of the state. In the same vein, the October Revolution in Russia also annulled the previous property Constitution through massive nationalization. Then post-socialist legal systems abolished the Constitution of socialist property through privatization and redistribution of property².

The lack of economic progress can become a phenomenon of suppression through an unbearable constrain of vulnerable groups that gradually find themselves under the influence of social groups, which are concerned only with the prosperity of their economic position, a fact found in most of the state of the former socialist camp where political forces, which have influence over the strategic law enforcement bodies, instead of fighting poverty, they are only interested in increasing tariffs and prices for products and services in order to increase the transactions carried out by companies registered in offshore with the respective members as beneficiaries.

The state of vulnerability produced by economic factors can be used by certain political forces to monopolize power through the wide spread of false statements to restore economic equity, a fact easily noted in the middle of the twentieth century by the seizure of power by fascist regimes in some European states in a manifest economic depression.

¹ Baieș S., Volcinschi V., Băieșu A., Cebotari V. Drept Civil. Drepturile reale. Teoria generală a obligațiilor. Volumul II. Chișinău: Cartier juridic, 2005, p. 47.

² Mattei U., Baieș, S., Roșca, N. Principiile fundamentale ale dreptului de proprietate, Ed. ARC, 2000, p. 29.

Professor Andrei Smochina suggests that: the harsh phenomena of economic crises, the world economic crisis of 1929-1933 contributed to a new tension of social and class, national contradictions, deepening political stability, ruling circles fighting to stop the activity of state and law democratic institutions and consolidation of political regimes. Throughout the region, the tendencies of the crisis of Parlamentarium emerged, which lacked sustained traditions and a social basis, the intervention of the state bureaucratic apparatus in all areas of political life rejecting constitutional rights and freedoms.

These tendencies, at the final stage of the world economic crisis, contributed to the emergence of the dictatorial, military-authoritarian regime in Bulgaria, to the accentuation of authoritarian principles and institutes in the new constitutions adopted in Yugoslavia (1931), Poland (1935), Romania (1938), which marginalized the powers of representative bodies, but extended the powers of the executive power, the army and the entire administrative apparatus³.

Thus, the state of poverty favors dictatorships, because human rights are not the daily concerns of a hungry population and its rulers⁴.

The way of organizing and functioning of the state economic activity is based on such institutions as the principles of the free market, free trade, interference in private affairs, etc., which creates a guarantee that the state power is exercised under the right supervision of society. To the above mentioned as an example we can take the state of Chile, which in the late 80s of the twentieth century, was created as a state with an efficient and dynamic economy to the removal of the dictatorship and the establishment of a constitutional legal regime that corresponded to an extent with the principles above indicated.

Another concept that refers to the way of organizing and exercising power within the state is the form of government that also, in turn, is independent on the level of economic development of the state. The absence of social fulfillments makes the activity of the parliament, the supreme legislative body, ineffective, because being a collegial body that brings together representatives of different social groups with conflicting interests leads to the existence of an impossibility of compromise characterized by political skirmishes that makes it impossible to adopt well-considered decisions.

International practice confirms that all economic crises produced over time have certain legal consequences, the most frequent being the increase in the power of the head of state and the state administration, carried out at the expense of the legislative authority, namely the parliament, which until the end can materialize with its very liquidation. As an example we can serve the 1926 coup d'état in Poland, generated by the

economic crisis that contributed to the introduction of an authoritarian dictatorial regime, built by the Constitution of 1935. A first step being the anti-democratic amendment introduced in the Constitution of Poland in 1926, when the president empowered (art. 44) with the right to adopt executive decrees "in cases of state necessity" that "had the power of law". Based on the provisions of the Constitution of 1935, the source and bearer of state power was the president, responsible only to "God and history". There was introduced a undemocratic and very complicated electoral system of electing the head of the state, which was determined by the president, as well as the way the candidate acceded to this position, which did not exclude his own proposal for the post of President. The activity of the Sejm and the Senate, which was appointed by the president and 1/3 of the members, had a subordinate character, since the president had the right not only to adopt decrees, with the power of law, to convene and dissolve the Sejm and the Senate, but also, moreover, to amend the Constitution⁵.

Such anti-democratic changes to the Constitution can also be observed in the Constitution of Czechoslovakia of 1927, where the president of the country was assigned such powers as the right to make changes to the Constitution. In Hungary, in 1926, the general electoral right was canceled, where the upper house of parliament (Senate) was restored, which included representatives of judicial circles, the generalities and persons appointed personally by Admiral Horthy Milos⁶.

The inability of the Economic Recovery also endangers also the fundamental human rights, regardless of their nature. The increasingly sharp contrast between human rights and public freedoms, which ultimately are both categories of human rights, makes disadvantaged circles turn their demands into such an intense social agitation that the freedoms won, specific to the first generation, appear as sources of chronic disorder, of chaos, and not of democracy. This new perception, due primarily to economic factors, leads to a reaction of power to limit disorder. It will tempt a calming of things by restricting the human rights of the first generation, by a reduction in the sphere of personal autonomy of which they are based⁷.

The above fact testifies to the existence of the legality that in a modern economy the more owners or separate economic units there are, the greater the number of subjects with a self-interest to participate in government. Only this number of owners depends on the level of monopolization of the state's economy, that is, on the legalities of redistribution of state resources. Respectively, the concentration of property in the same hand could limit the space for activity of other owners that would negatively influence the formation of the democratic regime or make it generally impossible.

³ Smochină A. *Istoria Universală a statului și dreptului*. Ediția a 3-a, Chișinău: F.E.P. „Tipografia Centrală”, 2013, 552 p., p. 468-469.

⁴ Dogaru I., Dănișor D.-C. *Drepturile omului și libertățile publice*. Chișinău: Editura Zamolse, 1998, p. 55.

⁵ Smochină A. *Istoria Universală a statului și dreptului*, Epoca Modernă și Contemporană. Chișinău: F.E.P. „Tipografia Centrală”, 2002, p. 204.

⁶ Smochină A. *Istoria Universală a statului și dreptului*, Epoca Modernă și Contemporană. Chișinău: F.E.P. „Tipografia Centrală”, 2002, p. 204.

⁷ Dogaru I., Dănișor D.-C. *Drepturile omului și libertățile publice*. Chișinău: Editura Zamolse, 1998, p. 54.

Democracy, as a form of political organization of society that proclaims the principle of the possession of power by the people, is based on the existence of a social group of economically formed middle class, which can only be obtained by the most efficient distribution of material means to the widest possible mass of people. A gesture that would provide an effective guarantee of political and civil rights. It is important, in this context, to mention that if the state is rich in terms of mineral deposits it does not mean that it fully respects the fundamental human rights and freedoms. For example, the United Arab Emirates or Saudi Arabia have an indication of high gross national product (GNP), but a protection of human rights below the level of countries such as Greece or Portugal, which have a much lower GNP. The distribution of wealth to a large middle class is a guarantor of respect for Human Rights⁸.

A prosperous economy, created on the principles of de-monopolization, is that economy where business is structured in three sectors: large, small and medium business. A considerable part of the property is invested in the form of capital so that small and medium-sized owners do not simply possess any property, but act relatively independently, not being under the direct control of monopolies, of large business.

Such a reality makes the economy of the state to be formed by a community of owners, where everyone has his particular interests, at the same time, being united by the general political interest. That is, ensuring the non-interference of the state in private affairs that would mean fulfilling the passive obligation such as legal regulation, property protection, formation of favorable climate for economic activity, support of small business, promotion of an adequate fiscal policy, etc. In such a way, the state bears the common pressure of several economically, politically independent subjects, who are interested in defending their interests in tax imposition, and in the adoption of laws, which justifies the activity of the parliament economically. It coordinating their interests, and the owners are only interested in the public power to be a safe and capable mechanism to achieve compliance with laws, to maintain the legal order, to ensure fair competition and financial stability, this is currently nonexistent in the Republic of Moldova due to the neglect of small business.

A. P. Iiescu argues that property, being a condition and source of individuality and freedom, fulfills its functions only when it is private property, individual property dispersed among the members of society: the dispersal of property frees not only those members of society who end up having an important patrimony, but also those whose property is reduced, because it abolishes the monopoly of power, multiplies decision centers and gives all people the opportunity to choose freely between several variants of action, it gives them equal opportunities. "...the more independent the individual is from public resources and institutions (...), the

higher is his degree of freedom. On the contrary, dependence on public resources leads to a dependence on the decisions of the institutions that administer those resources, thus to a reduction in individual freedom..."⁹.

A de-monopolized economic system with a considerable number of independent owners is the perfect environment that would benefit the development of democratic political regimes. The degree of development and monopolization of the economy of the state has tangents on the territorial organization of the state. Thus, economic progress and the existence of a large number of owners contribute to territorial consolidation, insofar as this is necessary for the creation of a single economic space, for the movement of goods, finance and labor. In conditions of economic crisis, on the contrary, the state is unable to fully ensure its territorial integrity, increasing the risk of political and administrative separation of territories in order to promote local interests.

We have analyzed what means an economy based on the most efficient distribution of material means to the widest possible mass of people with its effects. In cases where "limited resources" are concentrated in the hands of a small number of owners, political oligarchy is facilitated, situations when large owners seize control over the state, and their financial and economic power contributes to this fact.

Thus, in the conditions of monopolistic economy, the state becomes a tool of ensuring the economic and political interests of monopolies. In particular, it is possible to create collegial bodies, in the composition of which the leaders of economic clans are represented, for example, the Council of Emirs in the United Arab Emirates¹⁰.

The concentration of limited resources and the monopolization of the economy also influence the character of territorial organization. In cases where monopolies do not territorially divide the sphere of economic influence, they do not have the interest of territorial division. But if their economic interests are limited by a certain space, then there is an orientation towards the political and administrative separation of territorial units, towards the formation of federations, which is fully felt in the southern region of the Republic of Moldova, in the Gagauzery region, which also endangers the territorial integrity of the state.

The monopoly fulfills the role of political and administrative institution, ensuring by itself Legal Regulation, determining the legal status of man, controlling military formations and justice bodies. This role was played until recently by monopolistic companies of South African origin from Namibia. It was only through the competition of the international community that the nation state was established in this country¹¹. Likewise, in the more distant past, Dutch, French, Eng-

^{8 8} Dogaru I., Dănișor D.-C. Drepturile omului și libertățile publice. Chișinău: Editura Zamolse, 1998, p. 55.

^{9 9} Iiescu A.-P. Liberalismul. Între succese și iluzii. București: Editura: ALL, 1998, p. 47-49.

¹⁰ Конституционное право зарубежных стран: Учебник для вузов / Под общ. ред. чл.-корр. РАН, проф. М. В. Баглая, д.ю.н., проф. Ю. И. Лейбо и д.ю.н., проф. Л. М. Энттина,- М.: Норма, 2004, с. 756-759.

¹¹ <http://geo.historic.ru/>, http://www.worldrover.com/history/namibia_history.html

lish, Portuguese and other East - and West-Indian companies administered the colonial territories¹². "In principle, these companies were much like state bodies (they had police, could build cities and fortresses, minted coins, decide on issues of declaring war and concluding peace on the territory of the colony), and although they owned private capital, they were considered legal entities of public Law"¹³.

Another situation exists when the regulation of the economy by the public power is focused on ensuring the interests of the administration, not the owners. In this case, a harsh authoritarian economic regime is created, which is externalized by merging power and property in the hands of the groups that hold political power, which leads to the braking of the processes of democratization of society¹⁴.

We have pointed out above that the interests of large owners limit the power of the state, but it is much easier to obey several large economic units to state control than many small units. Thus, it is even easier for the state to subdue its monopolies than the de-monopolized economy, because monopolies leave no room for other owners able to declare their interests. In this context, in ancient China the rulers, tending to absolute political power, considered it necessary to eliminate the landowners, establishing control over aristocratic land ownership right up to the confiscation of domains for the benefit of the state¹⁵. At present, an eloquent example of the state's obedience of large monopolists is the case of Khodorkovsky in the Russian Federation. As we have seen, dependent participants of the economic system relatively calmly endure the subordination of monopoly by state power. In the economic sense, this appears as a more or less successful change of the "master".

Thus, the state or political group, pursuing the goal of consolidating power, political unity, can obtain political and economic control over the created monopolies and over the economy in general, advancing towards a higher level of monopolism - state monopolism. The state becomes the main, if not the only master, the only owner. Any source of income directly or indirectly depends on the state. States with such an economic situation, as a rule, gain the highest degree of power over society and become the most politically monopolized¹⁶.

From the above, in situations when the state has influence over the majority owners or their most important objects (strategic branches) political stability is obvious, even if some problems arise, they are not generated by monopolism, but by economic crises, given that in situations of state monopoly the economic system becomes less efficient. Thus, the interdependence

between the level of development of the state's economy and the stability of the social system takes place because poverty and lack of economic progress destroy the state.

The process of increasing the influence of the state on the state economic aspect also causes certain political-judicial consequences; therefore, simple citizen deprived of his property as a state of affairs loses the aspect of its real value. Thus, a considerable part of the population, unwilling to eliminate its natural tendency towards well-being, violates the legal norm, falling into the category of citizens who acquire wealth through illicit means or as privileges of service. We find such an approach in Sergiu Baies statement: "I emphasized a difference of conscience of individuals from Western Europe, from those from the ex-Soviet space. The communist policy of expropriation and removal from the circuit of land and means of production deprived the citizen of the spirit of the owner. Many workers in industry and agriculture earned substantial income from embezzlement at their place of work or other parts of "socialist property" and did so without a conscience. Of course, embezzlement was condemned by the system, but it was often agreed by other members of society"¹⁷.

The system, in which crimes or lawlessness of civil servants become a norm of social life, is typical not only of twentieth-century socialism. History reports that even in ancient Sparta, transformed by the reforms of Lycurgus, the right of private property was strictly limited, and on the other hand, successful robbery was unofficially approved¹⁸.

We can firmly say that state monopolism does not necessarily change the form of government, rather the historical conditions of monopolization and development of statehood lead to the modification of the form of government because history confirms that monopolistic states existed both in the form of monarchies and in the form of republics.

The fact is that states that have accepted the democratic regime, are taking measures to create a stable economic base and stable democratic organization. Thus, economic rights are enshrined in constitutions as fundamental rights, the constitution obliging the state to support and defend such institutions as private property, inheritance, the right to work, labor protection, right to strike, the right to affiliate in syndicate, etc. Such measures are of enormous importance not only in economic-legal aspect, but also in constitutional aspect.

The practice of existence of the Republic of Moldova as a sovereign state confirms that, however, those constitutional provisions are more effective that are aimed at creating a regime of non-interference of the state in the overall economic activity, the Constitution

¹² Всемирная история. - Т. 1. 4-е изд., испр. и перераб./Глав. ред. М. Аксёнова. - М.: Аванта+, 1997, с. 610-612

¹³ Roşca N., Baieş S. Dreptul afacerilor. Volumul I. Chişinău: F.E.-P. „Tipogr. Centrală”. 2004, p. 149.

¹⁴ Медушевский, А. Н. Сравнительное конституционное право и политические институты. Москва: ГУ ВШЭ, 2002, с. 330.

¹⁵ Прудников, М.Н., История государства и права зарубежных стран. Серия «Высшее образование» Ростов-на-Дону. Изд-во „Феникс”, 2003, с.46.

¹⁶ Арановский, К. В. Государственное право зарубежных стран. Учебное пособие. Москва: ИД «Форум»; ИНФРА-М, - 2000, с. 63.

¹⁷ Mattei U., Baieş S., Roşca N. Principiile fundamentale ale dreptului de proprietate, Ed. ARC, 2000, p. 210.

¹⁸ Хачатурян, В. М. История мировых цивилизаций. Москва: Издательский дом „Дрофа”, 1998, с. 55-56.

establishing only the empowerment of the state in directing the economy only by means of financial and fiscal policies.

Conclusions

From the above we can conclude that the interaction between economic human rights as the basis of the economic system and the social system highlights some legalities:

- The stability of the social system directly depends on the level of state economic development, economic stability, so social peace can exist only if the majority of members of society consider their economic condition satisfactory.
- The undeveloped economy stops the formation of a stable social organization and the application of constitutional principles of the rule of law, and an inefficient economic system gives the rise to deficits and disillusionment, which in turn leads people to satisfy economic interests by methods contrary to public order, which causes stability disruption.
- The greater the share of small and medium-sized owner in the economy, the more effective is the control of civil society over state power.

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